

target CRM	REE	Si, Mn, Al, B, Cu, Nb, V, P	Al, Si, Cu, Mg, Mn, Ni, Ti, Ga, V	Al, Si, Mn, Ni, Ti, Cu, Mg	Mg	Cu	Cu	La	Pt, Pd, Rh		
application/waste flow	NdFeB-magnets (in electric/traction motors)	UHSS and AHSS in chassis (BIW)	wrought Al (5000x, 6000x, 7000x series) in BIW	cast Al in wheels	Mg alloys (seat frame and front-end frame, high temperature resistant parts such as cylinder block, and moving parts such as the wheel)	embedded electronics	electric/traction motors	catalytic converters	catalytic converters		
EoL treatment scenario without CRM recovery	The magnets, along with the car, are sent to the shredder and eventually end up in the magnetic separator together with the other magnetic components	Common steel recycling and recovery processes, downcycling through mixing possible, possibility only to produce mild steel and not an UHSS/AHSS high quality steel	Common Al recycling and recovery processes, which include the mixing of cast and wrought Al-containing parts, downcycling in to cast Al or ending up as surplus scrap	Entire gets shredded without complete liberation, cast Al ends up in wrong output fractions like plastics or other metal fractions or separated Al fraction does not have the required purity and is used for other metallurgical processes	Entire car gets shredded with or without complete liberation, Mg alloys end up in Al fraction, Mg oxidizes easily at high temperatures, especially when not protected, MgO ends up in slags	Entire car gets shredded without complete liberation, Cu from the electronics ends up in wrong output fractions like plastics or other metal fraction due to incomplete separation, Cu ends up in landfills, incineration ashes or impurity in iron or Al	Entire car gets shredded without complete liberation, Cu in electric motors ends up in wrong output fractions like plastics or other metal fraction due to incomplete separation, Cu ends up in landfills, incineration ashes or impurity in iron or Al	Separation of the catalytic converters and further disassembly, catalysts end up in integrated copper smelter and La in the slags	Cars are exported and PGMs from catalysts not recovered, or PGMs are lost during use phase of the car		
(Partially) existing or potential EoL treatment scenario with CRM recovery	Selective removal followed by either hydrometallurgical or pyrometallurgical processes (aiming at the recovery of the elements from the magnet)	Separation of UHSS and AHSS through advanced sorting mechanisms to ensure clean fractions and avoid downcycling, functional recycling of CRMs using pyrometallurgy for secondary steel production, CRMs contained in the alloys remain in the alloys (aiming at the recovery of the alloy)	Separation of different wrought Al alloys (1000x, 2000x, 3000x, 4000x, 5000x, 6000x, 7000x series) through advanced sorting technologies (e.g. LIBS) to ensure high quality wrought Al scrap, followed by remelting of the sorted wrought Al with functional recovery of alloying elements	Separation of cast and wrought Al alloys through advanced sorting technologies (e.g. LIBS), followed by remelting of the sorted cast Al with functional recovery of alloying elements	Separation of Mg alloys through advanced sorting technologies (e.g. LIBS), followed by remelting of the sorted Mg alloys	Separation of electronics, electronics as input to integrated Cu smelters	Separation of the motor and further disassembly to isolate the Cu-containing components/parts as input to integrated Cu smelters	Separation of the catalytic converters and further disassembly, the extraction of La can be achieved via the following routes: Route 1: Hydrometallurgical route - leaching with nitric acid (Alcaraz et al. 2022), Route 2: Selective precipitation method (Maidel et al. 2019)	Separation of the catalytic converters as input to integrated Cu smelters where Ag, Au, and Pd can be recovered by electrowinning from Cu anode slime (CAS) (Hagelüken, 2006)		
Nb.	Criteria (affecting recoverability)	How to evaluate the criteria?									
design/input-specific criteria											
1.1	Dissipation and heterogeneity in product/waste flow (accumulation and mass fraction within a product/waste flow)	How dissipated is the CRM and/or the CRM containing application in the product? Is the CRM and/or CRM containing application accumulated in specific components? Is the CRM accumulated/enriched in parts of the waste flow or is it more widely distributed within the waste flow? How is the CRM mass fraction in relation to the ore grade (in the application/component/product/parts of the waste flow)?	The permanent magnets in the car are accumulated in electric traction motors (electric and hybrid vehicles). The REE content in NdFeB magnets is around 30%. The magnets have a weight of around 3 kg, depending on the car size. In addition to this, there are certain permanent magnets in sensors, speakers and audio systems, which are of less relevance due to their small size.	In modern car designs, UHSS, AHSS and mild steel are often combined within a single component or assembly, mainly in the so called "general component" family including BIW, chassis, wheels, etc.. The weight of AHSS from a standard petrol car produced in 2022 is around 120 kg. The weight of UHSS from a standard petrol car produced in 2022 is around 100 kg.	Wrought Al in BIW is not highly dissipated - it tends to be accumulated in specific subcomponents, such as outer body panels, crash management systems and structural reinforcements. The most common alloy types are 6xxx and 7xxx Al alloys. The mass of the 6xxx series in the "general component" component family is around 25 kg in case of a standard petrol car produced in 2022. The weight of the general component is around 936 kg.	Cast Al is accumulated in wheels. The mass of the cast Al alloys in the "general component" component family is around 135 kg in case of a standard petrol car produced in 2022. The weight of the general component is around 936 kg.	Mg alloys can be found in the interior structures, such as seat frames, steering wheel frames. In addition to this, Mg alloys can be found in chassis.	Cu is used extensively in automotive electronics, including wiring harnesses, PCBs in electronic control units, infotainment, sensors, connectors, relays, and fuses. These components are small, dispersed, and embedded in plastic or composite housings. Cu in automotive electronics is highly enriched compared to natural ores. The weight of the embedded electronics cables from a standard battery electric car produced in 2022 is around 17 kg (mass fraction of Cu: 0.85). The weight of actuators, controllers and headlights is around 55 kg in (mass fraction of Cu: 0.04).	Cu in the traction motors of electric vehicles is highly concentrated and minimally dissipated. Cu in electric motors is highly enriched compared to natural ores. The mass fraction of Cu in the traction motors is 0.99. The weight of a traction motor from a standard battery electric car produced in 2022 is around 33 kg.	La is concentrated in catalytic converters. La is used in ceria-lanthanum oxide mixtures. It is chemically bound in the wash coat of catalytic converters and not easily separable. Its mass fraction in the catalytic converter is lower than in natural ores.	Pt, Pd and Rh are concentrated in catalytic converters, specifically in the catalyst material. The PGM mass fraction in catalytic converters is significantly higher than in natural ores.
1.2	Change in product design/input (changes in quantities, replacements, etc.)	What are the current developments regarding change in product design, especially change in CRM quantities and replacements? Are there expected input changes that will affect the waste flow?	Changes in product design are expected. For example, the benefits of doping NdFeB magnets with indium could lead to the modification of microstructure, improvement of corrosion resistance and magnetic characteristics (Li et al. 2024).	In the future, the increased use of UHSS and 3rd Gen AHSS is highly expected in order to improve crash safety, reduce vehicle weights, and meet CO2 and fuel economy regulations (Pierce & Slowik, 2025)	Wrought Al (mainly 5000x, 6000x and 7000x series) is increasingly used in outer panels (hoods, doors, trunk lids), crash management systems, floor and roof structures. In some cases, wrought Al is being replaced by castings or multi-material assemblies to reduce costs or improve manufacturability. There is an increasing usage trend. There are expected alloy shifts, especially to 6000x.	Car manufacturers are increasingly using Al — not only in wheels but across the body, chassis, and powertrain — driving the demand for improved cast Al alloys and shifts in series to balance performance, cost, weight, and sustainability.	A rising trend in magnesium alloy adoption for vehicles is expected, driven by the need for lightweighting to improve fuel efficiency, reduce emissions, and enhance EV range.	More embedded electronics, more Cu in EV electronics, more Al wiring	Increased Cu content in electric motors is expected	Manufacturers are reducing La content due to CRM status of La in the EU and other regions, cost volatility and supply chain risks, and advances in ceria-zirconia formulations that reduce or eliminate the need for La.	Current trends in product design are seeing a shift in the use of PGMs, particularly a move towards substituting Pd with Pt in catalytic converters for gasoline vehicles. This shift is driven by price fluctuations, supply chain constraints, and advancements in automotive technology, including the rise of EVs.
1.3	Product information and labelling (identifiability of CRM containing applications and components)	Does the product labelling provide sufficient information about the mass fraction and location of CRM in the product? Is there a required or voluntary labelling?	The CRM Act requires labelling of permanent magnets in electric motors indicating: - the amount of permanent magnets in the product - the types of permanent magnets The label design and implementation is currently under development (until 2026). The data carrier should contain: - producer information - information on weight, location, and chemical composition of the permanent magnets - information regarding removal of the permanent magnets	Currently, product labelling does not provide sufficient information about the mass fraction or location of UHSS or AHSS in the vehicle chassis (proprietary and semi-proprietary information).	IMDS provides the material data sheet or "label" at the material/substance level for wrought Al, but not a commercial or consumer-facing product label (Pollok et al. 2004).	IMDS provides the material data sheet or "label" at the material/substance level for cast Al, but not a commercial or consumer-facing product label (Pollok et al. 2004).	Currently, product labelling does not provide sufficient information about the mass fraction or location of Mg alloys in components such as the seat frame, wheel, or cylinder block of vehicles.	Currently, product labelling does not provide sufficient information about the mass fraction or location of Cu in automotive electronics.	Product labelling for electric traction motors is not yet in place. It is expected to follow future policy frameworks for component traceability, such as the Digital Product Passport (DPP).	Currently, product labelling does not provide sufficient information about the mass fraction or location of La in three-way catalytic converters.	Product labelling for catalytic converters does typically not include detailed information on the mass fraction of PGMs. While there are labelling requirements for hazardous materials and recycling symbols, specific details about PGM content are generally not provided on the product label.

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waste flow-specific criteria											
2.1	Dissipation in waste flow	How high is the mass fraction of the CRM in the (collected) waste flow (in relation to the ore grade)? How is the CRM containing application collected (e.g. application-, component-, product-level, mixed with other products)? Is there a pre-sorting of components or products? Is there a pre-sorting regarding input material/parts of the waste flow?	Most ELVs are shredded without prior removal of magnets.	ELVs containing UHSS and AHSS are collected and brought to shredders or dismantling plants.	The BIW is not typically separated before shredding.	The wheels are typically not separated before shredding.	Most Mg-alloy components in ELVs are not systematically separated before shredding.	The removal of Cu wires as well as the electronics during the dismantling process before the shredding is very labour-intensive and often not done.	The electric motor is typically not separated before shredding.	Catalytic converters are removed before shredding.	Catalytic converters are removed before shredding. The mass fraction of PGMs in collected waste flows, such as spent catalytic converters is with around 2000 ppm significantly higher than in natural ores (1-10 ppm) (SCREEN CRMs fact sheet, 2023; Van Rythoven, 2024)
2.2	Mineralogical state	In which mineralogical state is the CRM in the application or waste flow (e.g. metal, oxide, etc.)?	Nd ₂ Fe ₁₄ B phase is the main magnetic phase in NdFeB magnets. It is a metallic intermetallic compound.	Metal alloy	Metal alloy	Metal alloy	Metal alloy	Native metal	Native metal	La ₂ O ₃ (lanthanum oxide)	In catalytic converters, PGMs are primarily found in the following mineralogical states: native metal (most common), oxides (under high-temperature conditions, these metals can form oxides)
2.3	Product and/or component collection (collection and return rates)	How high are the collection and return rates? Why are they high/low?	The collection and return rates for ELVs are generally high. This is due to regulatory aspects (ELV Directive 2000/53/EC), established infrastructure, and EPR (Vermeulen, et al. 2011). However, there is still a "vehicle gap" which means that an important share of missing vehicles subject to the ELV Directive are not collected.	The collection and return rates for ELVs are generally high. This is due to regulatory aspects (ELV Directive 2000/53/EC), established infrastructure, and EPR (Vermeulen, et al. 2011). However, there is still a "vehicle gap" of missing vehicle with unknown whereabouts.	The collection and return rates for ELVs are generally high. This is due to regulatory aspects (ELV Directive 2000/53/EC), established infrastructure, and EPR (Vermeulen, et al. 2011). However, there is still a "vehicle gap" of missing vehicle with unknown whereabouts.	The collection and return rates for ELVs are generally high. This is due to regulatory aspects (ELV Directive 2000/53/EC), established infrastructure, and EPR (Vermeulen, et al. 2011). However, there is still a "vehicle gap" of missing vehicle with unknown whereabouts.	The collection and return rates for ELVs are generally high. This is due to regulatory aspects (ELV Directive 2000/53/EC), established infrastructure, and EPR (Vermeulen, et al. 2011). However, there is still a "vehicle gap" of missing vehicle with unknown whereabouts.	The collection and return rates for ELVs are generally high. This is due to regulatory aspects (ELV Directive 2000/53/EC), established infrastructure, and EPR (Vermeulen, et al. 2011). However, there is still a "vehicle gap" of missing vehicle with unknown whereabouts.	The collection and return rates for ELVs are generally high. This is due to regulatory aspects (ELV Directive 2000/53/EC), established infrastructure, and EPR (Vermeulen, et al. 2011). However, there is still a "vehicle gap" of missing vehicle with unknown whereabouts.	The collection and return rates for ELVs are generally high. This is due to regulatory aspects (ELV Directive 2000/53/EC), established infrastructure, and EPR (Vermeulen, et al. 2011). However, there is still a "vehicle gap" of missing vehicle with unknown whereabouts.	The collection and return rates for ELVs are generally high. This is due to regulatory aspects (ELV Directive 2000/53/EC), established infrastructure, and EPR (Vermeulen, et al. 2011). However, there is still a "vehicle gap" of missing vehicle with unknown whereabouts.
2.4	Current waste generated	Which waste quantities are currently generated?	It is difficult to quantify the exact waste quantities. However, it is obvious that EVs are significant contributors to permanent magnet waste in the EU. 35% of the permanent magnets are going to cars (BEV, HEV, PHEV), 12% to windmills, 25% to electronics (Howley et al., n.d.).	200-400 kg/car	400-800 kg/car (both wrought and cast Al)	400-800 kg/car (both wrought and cast Al)	Total Mg alloy mass per vehicle: ~4-10 kg (Levik et al., 2021)	8-15 kg/petrol and diesel cars, 15-25 kg/HEV, PHEV, BEV	20-30 kg Cu/EVs	The waste quantities generated from catalytic converters in the EU are substantial due to the high number of vehicles reaching the end of their life cycle (CYCLEON Project, 1999).	The waste quantities generated from catalytic converters in the EU are substantial due to the high number of vehicles reaching the end of their life cycle (CYCLEON Project, 1999).
2.5	Future waste generated	Which waste quantities are expected to be generated in the future?	Increasing waste quantities are expected in the future (Gauß et al., 2021).	Increasing waste quantities are expected in the future, UHSS and AHSS are used for lightweighting purposes (European Aluminum Association, 2022).	Increasing waste quantities are expected in the future	Increasing waste quantities are expected in the future	Increasing waste quantities are expected in the future (middle class and high-end vehicles)	Increasing waste quantities are expected in the future due to high-power electronics in BEV, PHEV and HEV	Increasing waste quantities are expected in the future	Despite the rise of BEVs, gasoline and hybrid vehicles will continue to be produced, ensuring a steady generation of catalytic converter waste (Le Breton, 2025)	Despite the rise of BEVs, gasoline and hybrid vehicles will continue to be produced, ensuring a steady generation of catalytic converter waste (Le Breton, 2025)
technical criteria											
3.1	Availability of identification technology for CRM containing application/material/component/product	Is there a technology to identify the CRM containing application/component/product to enable its recovery?	Permanent magnets are identifiable by the dismantling person in case of dismantling. Automated identification systems can identify permanent magnets.	Different steel grades can be detected with handheld XRF devices.	In many cases Al can be identified visually. LIBS and XRF technology can detect composition or Al series. However, XRF cannot detect light elements, like Li, Si, etc., so it is mainly used for Cu-containing alloys.	In many cases Al can be identified visually. LIBS and XRF technology can detect composition or Al series. However, XRF cannot detect light elements, like Li, Si, etc., so it is mainly used for Cu-containing alloys.	Mg alloys often end up in the Al fraction as they are not easy to identify and separate from Al alloys. LIBS and XRF technology can detect composition. However, XRF cannot detect light elements, like Li, Si, etc., so it is mainly used for Cu-containing alloys.	In most cases Cu can be identified visually due to its colour or based on its application, e.g. cables, coils.	In most cases Cu can be identified visually due to its colour or based on its application, e.g. cables, coils.	Catalytic converters can be identified visually. There are technologies to identify La such as XRF and LIBS.	Catalytic converters can be identified visually. All of them contain PGMs.

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3.2	Manual removability of CRM containing application/material/component (selective removal)	Is it possible to manually remove the CRM containing application or material from the product/waste flow (Is it screwed, glued, welded)?	Manual removal is possible, but depends on accessibility.	It is technically possible to manually remove certain chassis components or UHSS/AHSS parts from ELVs, feasibility and effort depend on how these parts are joined. Joining UHSS/AHSS in structural components can be done via welding, via adhesive bonding, via mechanical fasteners (bolts, screws), or sometimes via hybrid joining.	Depends on the connections (i.e., whether screws and bolts are used or something else). Manual sorting according to alloy type/series possible when the origin is known.	Depends on the connections (i.e., whether screws and bolts are used or something else). Manual sorting according to alloy type/series possible when the origin is known.	Some of the bolted parts containing Mg alloys can be manually removed such as seat frame, steering wheel frame, and transmission/clutch housing.	Most of the embedded electronics are manually removable, such as wiring harness (clipped, taped), connectors and terminals (plugged or clipped), PCBs (screwed or clipped), alternators and starters (bolted).	The manual removal of electric traction motors can be challenging. Firstly, because traction motors are heavy and integrated. Furthermore, Cu windings are embedded, and the disassembly requires specialized tools.	Catalytic converters in ELVs are typically manually removable.	Catalytic converters in ELVs are typically manually removable.
3.3	Automated removability of CRM containing application/material/components (selective removal)	Are processes available to remove the CRM containing application/component by automation? What is its TRL level?	Robotic dismantling to remove permanent magnets from electric motors is described in (Liang and Pham, 2025).	No	Robotic dismantling	Robotic dismantling	Robotic dismantling	Humanoid robot dismantling	Humanoid robot dismantling	There is no robotic dismantling	There is no robotic dismantling
3.4	Identifiability and separability of CRM containing material after liberation	Is it possible to identify and sort the CRM containing materials after liberation (e.g. shredding)? This can be without preceding removal/sorting or after preceding removal.	This is only relevant in case of prior concentration of a permanent magnet containing fraction. Due to the magnetic properties, it is difficult to separate permanent magnets from other magnetic ferrous metals.	Advanced sensor-based sorting (XRF, LIBS)	Non-ferrous metals can be separated from a waste flow by eddy current separation. The non-ferrous metal fraction can be further separated by density separation or XRT sensor-based sorting devices into a Cu and Al fraction. Al scrap can be sorted according to alloy type or series with LIBS or other sensor-based sorting technologies. Sensor-based sorting technologies are limited to Al scrap with high mass fraction of alloying elements and low variability within the fractions that should be separated.	Non-ferrous metals can be separated from a waste flow by eddy current separation. The non-ferrous metal fraction can be further separated by density separation or XRT sensor-based sorting devices into a Cu and Al fraction. Al scrap can be sorted according to alloy type or series with LIBS or other sensor-based sorting technologies. Sensor-based sorting technologies are limited to Al scrap with high mass fraction of alloying elements and low variability within the fractions that should be separated.	Non-ferrous metals can be separated from a waste flow by eddy current separation. The non-ferrous metal fraction can be further separated by density separation or XRT sensor-based sorting devices into a heavy- (Cu) and light-weight (Al and Mg) fraction. The light metals can be separated from each other through spectrographic techniques to obtain a relatively pure Mg scrap flow suitable for melting (Wang et al., 2024)	Non-ferrous metals can be separated with eddy current separation. The non-ferrous metal fraction can be further separated by density separation into a Cu and Al fraction.	Non-ferrous metals can be separated with eddy current separation. The non-ferrous metal fraction can be further separated by density separation into a Cu and Al fraction.	There are technologies to identify La such as XRF and LIBS.	Metallurgical separation (based on the different melting temperatures)
3.5	Ability to concentrate CRM containing material / mechanically remove impurities	Is it possible to concentrate or to mechanically remove impurities from the CRM containing material flow?	This is only relevant in case of prior concentration of a permanent magnet containing fraction. Due to the magnetic properties, it is difficult to separate permanent magnets from other magnetic ferrous metals.	Certain impurities can partially be removed mechanically. Certain mechanical methods, such as magnetic separation, eddy current separation, air classification, density separation can remove some impurities. Recycling usually downcycles AHSS and UHSS into lower-grade steel.	Al scrap is separated from other fractions in a positive sorting process. Further removal of impurities is of less relevance. High quality requirements for positive sorting, losses in residues are taken into account to achieve quality requirements.	Al scrap is separated from other fractions in a positive sorting process. Further removal of impurities is of less relevance. High quality requirements for positive sorting, losses in residues are taken into account to achieve quality requirements.	Mg scrap is separated from other fractions in a positive sorting process. Further removal of impurities is of less relevance. High quality requirements for positive sorting, losses in residues are taken into account to achieve quality requirements.	Cu scrap is either collected separated at source or separated from other fractions after shredding in a positive sorting process. Pure fractions such as cables can be remelted after the removal of insulation. Further removal of impurities is of less relevance. Purity requirements of the input material for an integrated Cu smelter are low.	Cu scrap is either collected separated at source or separated from other fractions after shredding in a positive sorting process. Pure fractions such as cables can be remelted after the removal of insulation. Further removal of impurities is of less relevance. Purity requirements of the input material for an integrated Cu smelter are low.	Yes, it is technically possible to concentrate the lanthanum-containing flow during the recycling of catalytic converters, but it is not commonly done.	It is possible to concentrate and purify PGMs from material flows containing these metals.
3.6	Ability to thermally and/or chemically separate and refine CRMs from concentrates	Is there a thermal and/or chemical recovery technology for the CRM? What is its TRL level?	Different long-loop recycling technologies available for refining REE (liquid-liquid extraction, selective precipitation/bioleaching, liquid metal extraction, slagging). In case of short-loop recycling, technologies like smelting/strip-casting, hydrogen decrepitation, hydrogenation disproportionation desorption and recombination (HDDR), and melt-spinning are used. (Schönfeldt et al., 2024)	Currently, there is no widely adopted thermal or chemical recovery technology that can selectively recover Advanced High-Strength Steels (AHSS) or Ultra High-Strength Steels (UHSS) from chassis components	For functional recycling, purity requirements of the input material for remelting are high as the refining possibilities are limited. Mg as alloying element can be removed by different demagging processes (high energy and chemical input required). Most alloying elements remain in the metal phase, thus Al alloy needs to be diluted to achieve quality specification.	For functional recycling, purity requirements of the input material for remelting are high as the refining possibilities are limited. Mg as alloying element can be removed by different demagging processes (high energy and chemical input required). Most alloying elements remain in the metal phase, thus Al alloy needs to be diluted to achieve quality specification.	For functional recycling, purity requirements of the input material for remelting are high as the refining possibilities are limited. Technologies are described in Wang et al. (2024).	Pure Cu scrap can be remelted, more complex waste flows can be used as an input material in an integrated Cu smelter.	Pure Cu scrap can be remelted, more complex waste flows can be used as an input material in an integrated Cu smelter.	The thermal and/or chemical recovery of La from the automotive catalyst is technically possible, but the recovery is not commonly practiced at industrial scale.	There are well-established thermal and chemical recovery technologies for PGMs primarily from secondary sources like spent catalysts.

target CRM	REE	Si, Mn, Al, B, Cu, Nb, V, P	Al, Si, Cu, Mg, Mn, Ni, Ti, Ga, V	Al, Si, Mn, Ni, Ti, Cu, Mg	Mg	Cu	Cu	La	Pt, Pd, Rh		
application/waste flow	NdFeB-magnets (in electric/traction motors)	UHSS and AHSS in chassis (BIW)	wrought Al (5000x, 6000x, 7000x series) in BIW	cast Al in wheels	Mg alloys (seat frame and front-end frame, high temperature resistant parts such as cylinder block, and moving parts such as the wheel)	embedded electronics	electric/traction motors	catalytic converters	catalytic converters		
EoL treatment scenario without CRM recovery	The magnets, along with the car, are sent to the shredder and eventually end up in the magnetic separator together with the other magnetic components	Common steel recycling and recovery processes, downcycling through mixing possible, possibility only to produce mild steel and not an UHSS/AHSS high quality steel	Common Al recycling and recovery processes, which include the mixing of cast and wrought Al-containing parts, downcycling in to cast Al or ending up as surplus scrap	Entire gets shredded without complete liberation, cast Al ends up in wrong output fractions like plastics or other metal fractions or separated Al fraction does not have the required purity and is used for other metallurgical processes	Entire car gets shredded with or without complete liberation, Mg alloys end up in Al fraction, Mg oxidizes easily at high temperatures, especially when not protected, MgO ends up in slags	Entire car gets shredded without complete liberation, Cu from the electronics ends up in wrong output fractions like plastics or other metal fraction due to incomplete separation, Cu ends up in landfills, incineration ashes or impurity in iron or Al	Entire car gets shredded without complete liberation, Cu in electric motors ends up in wrong output fractions like plastics or other metal fraction due to incomplete separation, Cu ends up in landfills, incineration ashes or impurity in iron or Al	Separation of the catalytic converters and further disassembly, catalysts end up in integrated copper smelter and La in the slags	Cars are exported and PGMs from catalysts not recovered, or PGMs are lost during use phase of the car		
(Partially) existing or potential EoL treatment scenario with CRM recovery	Selective removal followed by either hydrometallurgical or pyrometallurgical processes (aiming at the recovery of the elements from the magnet)	Separation of UHSS and AHSS through advanced sorting mechanisms to ensure clean fractions and avoid downcycling, functional recycling of CRMs using pyrometallurgy for secondary steel production, CRMs contained in the alloys remain in the alloys (aiming at the recovery of the alloy)	Separation of different wrought Al alloys (1000x, 2000x, 3000x, 4000x, 5000x, 6000x, 7000x series) through advanced sorting technologies (e.g. LIBS) to ensure high quality wrought Al scrap, followed by remelting of the sorted wrought Al with functional recovery of alloying elements	Separation of cast and wrought Al alloys through advanced sorting technologies (e.g. LIBS), followed by remelting of the sorted cast Al with functional recovery of alloying elements	Separation of Mg alloys through advanced sorting technologies (e.g. LIBS), followed by remelting of the sorted Mg alloys	Separation of electronics, electronics as input to integrated Cu smelters	Separation of the motor and further disassembly to isolate the Cu-containing components/parts as input to integrated Cu smelters	Separation of the catalytic converters and further disassembly, the extraction of La can be achieved via the following routes: Route 1: Hydrometallurgical route - leaching with nitric acid (Alcaraz et al. 2022), Route 2: Selective precipitation method (Maidel et al. 2019)	Separation of the catalytic converters as input to integrated Cu smelters where Ag, Au, and Pd can be recovered by electrowinning from Cu anode slime (CAS) (Hagelüken, 2006)		
Nb.	Criteria (affecting recoverability)	How to evaluate the criteria?									
economic criteria											
4.1	Market and quality of 2CRM	Is there a market for the 2CRM? What is the quality of the 2CRM compared to the primary one? How volatile is the market?	There are differences depending on the EoL pathway (reuse, short, or long-loop recycling). There is an emerging market for magnet-to-magnet (short-loop) recycling. Magnet-to-REE (long-loop) recycling is linked to the REE market. There are full scale magnet production facilities in Europe as well as short loop recycling activities at the pilot scale. There are few refining capacities in Europe but they are under development through strategic projects.	Yes, there is a remelting market for AHSS and UHSS.	There is an Al scrap market. Most of the time Al scrap is not sorted according to alloy type or series and can only be downcycled to cast Al or ends up as scrap surplus. Additionally, non-ferrous metal scrap which is a mix of Al, Cu and other alloys is traded and can be e.g. used as input material for an integrated Cu smelter where Al ends up in the slag.	There is an Al scrap market. Most of the time Al scrap is not sorted according to alloy type or series and can only be downcycled to cast Al or ends up as scrap surplus. Additionally, non-ferrous metal scrap which is a mix of Al, Cu and other alloys is traded and can be e.g. used as input material for an integrated Cu smelter where Al ends up in the slag.	There are different Mg scrap classes. However, most EoL Mg scrap is neither effectively recycled nor utilized (Wang et al., 2024).	There is a Cu scrap market.	There is a Cu scrap market.	A small but emerging market exists for recovered La from automotive catalytic converters.	There is a huge market for secondary PGMs.
4.2	Price competition of 2CRM with primary	Would it be cheaper to use the waste flow instead of an ore to recover the CRM?	There are differences depending on the EoL pathway (reuse, short, or long-loop recycling). Magnet-to-magnet recycling can be cheaper than primary production. Grade, purity and quantity of the feedstock play an important role.	The recovery of UHSS and AHSS from the chassis would be cheaper in comparison to the primary extraction of the iron ore, followed by the control of the alloy.	The price for Al scrap depends on its quality and the demand for that quality on the market. There is no direct price competition between primary and secondary Al. Not every quality can be achieved with secondary Al.	The price for Al scrap depends on its quality and the demand for that quality on the market. There is no direct price competition between primary and secondary Al. Not every quality can be achieved with secondary Al.	The price for Mg scrap depends on its quality and the demand for that quality on the market. There is no direct price competition between primary and secondary Mg. Not every quality can be achieved with secondary Mg.	There is no price difference between primary and secondary Cu.	There is no price difference between primary and secondary Cu.	Difficult to say	There is no price difference between primary and secondary Pt, Pd, Rh.
4.3	Economic incentives	Do specific economic incentives exist (tax related, fees, etc.) to recover the CRM? Are there other materials or elements driving the recovery?	There might be a rise in demand due to the requirements for recycled content in permanent magnets in the CRM Act.	Emission trading can be considered as an economic incentive in this regard	Remelting Al needs significantly lower temperature and therefore energy than primary Al production. Therefore, emission trading and in the future the Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM) can act as an economic incentive for Al recycling.	Remelting Al needs significantly lower temperature and therefore energy than primary Al production. Therefore, emission trading and in the future the Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM) can act as an economic incentive for Al recycling.	Remelting Mg needs significantly lower temperature and therefore energy than primary Al production. Therefore, emission trading and in the future the Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM) can act as an economic incentive for Al recycling.	There are no economic incentives related to taxes or fees, but Cu is a valuable material.	There are no economic incentives related to taxes or fees, but Cu is a valuable material.	No	Only profit-driven economic incentives

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Nb.	Criteria (affecting recoverability)	How to evaluate the criteria?									
4.4	Economically viable case studies	Are there (potentially) economically viable case studies for the recovery of the CRM? Does the value or the quantity of the CRM play a decisive role?	Different commercial NdFeB magnet recycling projects (e.g. by Heraeus REMLOY GmbH, HyProMag GmbH, RockLink GmbH, MagREESource) and research projects (e.g. REEPRODUCE, SUSMAGPRO). Four projects of REE recycling from magnets were granted the status as strategic project under the CRM Act.. Independent EU project (REE4EU): https://ree4eu.eu/	Steel is highly recyclable and WorldAutoSteel case studies treat end-of-life recycling as a major lifecycle credit. ArcelorMittal's XCarb and "smart carbon" activity demonstrate that high-quality, low-carbon steels can be produced with high shares of recycled scrap, showing a technically feasible circular pathway for automotive steels. However, practical recovery of AHSS/UHSS faces real-world constraints: most AHSS/UHSS end up in mixed ferrous scrap after shredding, tramp-element accumulation and grade heterogeneity complicate reuse and recycling, and targeted sorting or design-for-recycling measures are needed to realize closed-loop recycling at scale.	Achieving functional recycling of wrought Al alloys from ELVs is possible, but needs the implementation of further measures. Without upstream separation, most automotive Al scrap is melted into lower-value or mixed alloys (downcycling).	Cast Al from ELVs can generally be recycled more easily than wrought Al alloys, since casting grades tolerate higher levels of impurities such as Fe and Cu. However, this typically leads to downcycling of mixed Al scrap into cast alloys, rather than preserving the higher-value wrought grades.	No information	There are many operating Cu smelters using pure Cu scrap. Integrated smelters can recover more complex waste flows, like PBCs, filter dust, or electronic components.	There are many operating Cu smelters using pure Cu scrap. Integrated smelters can recover more complex waste flows, like PBCs, filter dust, or electronic components.	There are initiatives, but they are under development. Large recyclers (e.g., Umicore, Johnson Matthey and others) currently operate robust PGM recovery lines and are researching or partnering on hydrometallurgical routes to recover light REEs (Ce/La) from washcoats, or to adapt flows so REEs are captured instead of lost in slags/dust. However, mainstream industrial recovery of La from autocatalysts is still emerging rather than established as a standard output.	Applied in industrial scale
4.5	Recycling conflicts with other materials or elements (especially more valuable ones)	Is there a recycling conflict with other materials or elements, especially with more valuable ones in the product/waste flow?	If there is Cu available at the same time, the recovery of Cu is more economic than REE.	AHSS/UHSS frequently become part of general ferrous scrap streams and are remade into lower-grade steels (downcycling).	Al in composite components with Cu: Separation is usually focussing on Cu, less on Al due to low tolerance to impurities. Risk of downcycling, if the alloy types are not sorted	Al in composite components with Cu: Separation is usually focussing on Cu, less on Al due to low tolerance to impurities. Risk of downcycling, if the alloy types are not sorted	Al when the light-weight metal fraction is not further sorted	There are no recycling conflicts with other materials or elements. Cu recycling is amplified as it is a carrier element for precious metal recovery. REE, Al, Mg, Fe, Ta, and other slag forming elements are typically lost.	There are no recycling conflicts with other materials or elements. Cu recycling is amplified as it is a carrier element for precious metal recovery. REE, Al, Mg, Fe, Ta, and other slag forming elements are typically lost.	Pt, Pd, Rh	No
environmental criteria											
5.1	Logistics and infrastructure	How are the logistic and infrastructure requirements for the recovery process (process steps, distances, etc.)? Can existing infrastructure be used?	The total mass flows of magnets are low, thus logistics will become relevant when scaling recycling infrastructure. Currently the infrastructure for the recycling processes (pyrometallurgical, hydrometallurgical, or direct recycling) are under development.	Existing infrastructure can be used for the recovery of AHSS and UHSS especially for collection, dismantling, and remelting. To preserve the high-grade properties of AHSS/UHSS and enable closed-loop recycling, upgrades in sorting, identification, and traceability are essential.	There is an established infrastructure for Al recycling (sorting and remelting). LIBS is an emerging technology enabling higher quality recycling separating 5000 and 6000 series Al. To establish the necessary logistics, a minimum volume of Al scrap is needed.	There is an established infrastructure for Al recycling (sorting and remelting). LIBS is an emerging technology enabling higher quality recycling separating 5000 and 6000 series Al. To establish the necessary logistics, a minimum volume of Al scrap is needed.	Existing infrastructure can be partially used, especially dismantling. No established infrastructure for Mg recycling, most Mg scrap is neither effectively recycled nor utilized Wang et al. (2024).	There is an established infrastructure for Cu recycling, both direct remelting or integrated smelters for more complex waste flows.	There is an established infrastructure for Cu recycling, both direct remelting or integrated smelters for more complex waste flows.	The existing infrastructure can be used only for collection and dismantling. The full recovery of La requires specialized chemical processing infrastructure.	Established infrastructure
5.2	Energy and chemical requirements for separation and sorting	What are the energy and chemical requirements for mechanical separation and sorting?	Sorting is less relevant due to the lack of magnet separation technologies for diluted waste flows, only relevant if a component fraction concentrating NdFeB magnets gets shredded.	Energy and chemical requirements for recycling are much lower than for primary production (saving up to 75% energy) (Asmatulu & Asmatulu, 2011).	Increased sensor-based sorting requires pressurized air and increases electricity demand (Ludwig et al., 2022).	Increased sensor-based sorting requires pressurized air and increases electricity demand (Ludwig et al., 2022).	Increased sensor-based sorting requires pressurized air and increases electricity demand (Ludwig et al., 2022).	Less sorting effort due to higher impurity tolerance of the melting process.	Less sorting effort due to higher impurity tolerance of the melting process.	Mechanical separation alone is insufficient for La recovery. Energy use in mechanical steps is moderate (mainly crushing and grinding). Chemical processing is essential, with high chemical input and moderate energy use.	No information
5.3	Energy and chemical requirements for thermal and/or chemical recovery	What are the energy and chemical requirements for thermal and/or (bio)chemical recovery in comparison with primary production?	Ex-ante LCA of magnet recycling: Recovered NdFeB powders have lower impacts than primary powders for almost all impact categories (van Nielen et al., 2024). No comparisons for REE extraction known.	Energy and chemical requirements for recycling are much lower than for primary production (saving up to 75% energy) (Asmatulu & Asmatulu, 2011).	Energy and chemical requirements for recycling are much lower than for primary production (saving up to 75% energy) (Asmatulu & Asmatulu, 2011; EuRic, n.d.).	Energy and chemical requirements for recycling are much lower than for primary production (saving up to 95% energy) (Asmatulu & Asmatulu, 2011).	Depends on the processing and purification requirements and technologies Wang et al. (2024).	Energy and chemical requirements for recycling are much lower than for primary production (saving up to 85% energy) (Asmatulu & Asmatulu, 2011).	Energy and chemical requirements for recycling are much lower than for primary production (saving up to 85% energy) (Asmatulu & Asmatulu, 2011).	Chemical processing is essential, with high chemical input and moderate energy use.	Lower energy and chemical requirements than for mining and economical favourable, which is why precious metals are the recycling drivers.

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Nb.	Criteria (affecting recoverability)	How to evaluate the criteria?										
5.4	Recycling conflicts with hazardous substances	Is there a recycling conflict with hazardous substances? Are there hazardous substances in the respective application/waste flow? Will there be hazardous substances liberated during the recovery process? Can the hazardous substances be contained adequately?	Metallic coatings such as nickel can be removed using mechanical, pyrometallurgical, or hydrometallurgical methods, with no technical limitations or conflicts associated with these approaches (Orefice et al., 2019).	No	The hazardous substances in the application/waste flow are Cr, Pb, Cd, isocyanates, which can originate from conversion coatings, paintings and primers. Hazardous substances can be released during recovery, such as liberation of isocyanates, metal fumes, etc.	The hazardous substances in the application/waste flow are Cr, Pb, Cd, isocyanates, which can originate from conversion coatings, paintings and primers. Hazardous substances can be released during recovery, such as liberation of isocyanates, metal fumes, etc.	The hazardous substances in the application/waste flow are Cr, Pb, Cd, isocyanates, which can originate from conversion coatings, paintings and primers. Hazardous substances can be released during recovery, such as liberation of isocyanates, metal fumes, etc.	Element usually occurs in combination with brominated flame retardants, of which some are listed as persistent organic pollutants in the POP-Regulation, and other hazardous substances on PCBs. Integrated smelters can contribute to depollution. Only Hg is a problem.	No	There are certain hazardous substances, e.g. from insulation on windings halogenated or brominated formulations, which can be liberated during thermal processing, more precisely during pyrolysis and smelting. These are acid gases from halogenated compounds, heavy metal fumes, etc.	No	No
5.5	Environmental impacts	What are the environmental impacts of the 2CRM in comparison with the primary CRM? Is there any implemented/standardized calculation pathway for environmental impact assessment?	Ex-ante LCA of magnet recycling: Recovered NdFeB powders have lower impacts than primary powders for almost all impact categories (van Nielen et al., 2024). No comparisons for REE extraction known.	Energy and chemical requirements for recycling are much lower than for primary production (saving up to 75% energy) (Asmatulu & Asmatulu, 2011).	Energy and chemical requirements for recycling are much lower than for primary production (saving up to 75% energy) (Asmatulu & Asmatulu, 2011; EuRic, n.d.).	Energy and chemical requirements for recycling are much lower than for primary production (saving up to 95% energy) (Asmatulu & Asmatulu, 2011).	No information	Energy and chemical requirements for recycling are much lower than for primary production (saving up to 85% energy) (Asmatulu & Asmatulu, 2011).	Energy and chemical requirements for recycling are much lower than for primary production (saving up to 85% energy) (Asmatulu & Asmatulu, 2011).	No information	No information	No information
legal criteria												
6.1	Recovery targets	Are there material or element specific recovery targets?	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No		
6.2	Removal requirements	Are there any removal requirements related to the CRM containing application?	CRM Act requires information regarding removal of the permanent magnet on the label which will be required by 2026 for certain products with motors among them. Similar requirements are expected with the new ELV directive.	No	No	No	No	Discussion about potential regulations	Discussion about potential regulations	The catalytic converters need to be removed before shredding the car.	The catalyst need to be removed before shredding the car.	
6.3	Legal incentives	Are there any legal incentives for the recovery of the CRM such as special facilities in application, permission or registration processes?	If considered as strategic project under the CRM Act, projects can benefit from streamlined and predictable permitting procedures and support in gaining access to finance. Furthermore, the requirement for a recycled content in permanent magnets in the CRM Act can act as incentive for recycling projects.	There are legal frameworks and indirect incentives with recovery and recycling targets in the ELV Directive (2000/53/EC)	There are legal frameworks and indirect incentives with recovery and recycling targets in the ELV Directive (2000/53/EC)	There are legal frameworks and indirect incentives with recovery and recycling targets in the ELV Directive (2000/53/EC)	There are legal frameworks and indirect incentives with recovery and recycling targets in the ELV Directive (2000/53/EC)	There are legal frameworks and indirect incentives with recovery and recycling targets in the ELV Directive (2000/53/EC)	There are legal frameworks and indirect incentives with recovery and recycling targets in the ELV Directive (2000/53/EC)	No	If considered as strategic project under the CRM Act, projects can benefit from streamlined and predictable permitting procedures and support in gaining access to finance.	
6.4	End-of-waste criteria	Are there established end-of-waste criteria for 2CRM?	There are no end-of-waste criteria for permanent magnet waste/concentrates yet.	Metal Scrap Regulation	Metal Scrap Regulation	Metal Scrap Regulation	No	Copper Scrap Regulation	Copper Scrap Regulation	No	No	

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application/waste flow	NdFeB-magnets (in electric/traction motors)	UHSS and AHSS in chassis (BIW)	wrought Al (5000x, 6000x, 7000x series) in BIW	cast Al in wheels	Mg alloys (seat frame and front-end frame, high temperature resistant parts such as cylinder block, and moving parts such as the wheel)	embedded electronics	electric/traction motors	catalytic converters	catalytic converters
EoL treatment scenario without CRM recovery	The magnets, along with the car, are sent to the shredder and eventually end up in the magnetic separator together with the other magnetic components	Common steel recycling and recovery processes, downcycling through mixing possible, possibility only to produce mild steel and not an UHSS/AHSS high quality steel	Common Al recycling and recovery processes, which include the mixing of cast and wrought Al-containing parts, downcycling in to cast Al or ending up as surplus scrap	Entire gets shredded without complete liberation, cast Al ends up in wrong output fractions like plastics or other metal fractions or separated Al fraction does not have the required purity and is used for other metallurgical processes	Entire car gets shredded with or without complete liberation, Mg alloys end up in Al fraction, Mg oxidizes easily at high temperatures, especially when not protected, MgO ends up in slags	Entire car gets shredded without complete liberation, Cu from the electronics ends up in wrong output fractions like plastics or other metal fraction due to incomplete separation, Cu ends up in landfills, incineration ashes or impurity in iron or Al	Entire car gets shredded without complete liberation, Cu in electric motors ends up in wrong output fractions like plastics or other metal fraction due to incomplete separation, Cu ends up in landfills, incineration ashes or impurity in iron or Al	Separation of the catalytic converters and further disassembly, catalysts end up in tengrated copper smelter and La in the slags	Cars are exported and PGMs from catalysts not recovered, or PGMs are lost during use phase of the car
(Partially) existing or potential EoL treatment scenario with CRM recovery	Selective removal followed by either hydrometallurgical or pyrometallurgical processes (aiming at the recovery of the elements from the magnet)	Separation of UHSS and AHSS trough advanced sorting mechanisms to ensure clean fractions and avoid downcycling, functional recycling of CRMs using pyrometallurgy for secondary steel production, CRMs contained in the alloys remain in the alloys (aiming at the recovery of the alloy)	Separation of different wrought Al alloys (1000x, 2000x, 3000x, 4000x, 5000x, 6000x, 7000x series) through advanced sorting technologies (e.g. LIBS) to ensure high quality wrought Al scrap, followed by remelting of the sorted wrought Al with functional recovery of alloying elements	Separation of cast and wrought Al alloys through advanced sorting technologies (e.g. LIBS), followed by remelting of the sorted cast Al with functional recovery of alloying elements	Separation of Mg alloys through advanced sorting technologies (e.g. LIBS), followed by remelting of the sorted Mg alloys	Separation of electronics, electronics as input to integrated Cu smelters	Separation of the motor and further disassembly to isolate the Cu-containing components/parts as input to integrated Cu smelters	Separation of the catalytic converters and further disassembly, the extraction of La can be achieved via the following routes: Route 1: Hydrometallurgical route - leaching with nitric acid (Alcaraz et al. 2022), Route 2: Selective precipitation method (Maidel et al. 2019)	Separation of the catalytic converters as input to integrated Cu smelters where Ag, Au, and Pd can be recovered by electrowinning from Cu anode slime (CAS) (Hagelüken, 2006)
Nb.	Criteria (affecting recoverability)	How to evaluate the criteria?							

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Abbreviations used

AHSS	Advanced high strength steel
BEV	Battery Electric Vehicle
BIW	Body-in-white
CRM	Critical Raw Material
ELV	End-of-life vehicle
EoL	End-of-life
EPR	Extended Producer Responsibility
EU	European Union
EV	Electric Vehicle
HEV	Hybrid Electric Vehicle
LIBS	Laser-induced breakdown spectroscopy
NIR	Near-infrared
PGM	Platinum Group Metal
PHEV	Plug-in Hybrid Electric Vehicle
REE	Rare Earth Elements
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UHSS	Ultra high strength steel
XRF	X-ray fluorescence
XRT	X-ray transmission